

PHOTOCHEMICAL REACTION WITH SOME INORGANIC COLLOIDS AS ACTIVE AGENTS UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF LIGHT IN VARIOUS STATES OF POLARISATION. PART X. ON THE PHOTOCHEMICAL OXIDATION OF GLUCOSE BY POTASSIUM INDIGO-TETRASULPHONATE WITH TUNGSTIC ACID SOL AS PHOTOCATALYST.

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Experimental arrangement was the same as in Part I of this series. Pure potassium indigo-tetrasulphonate (supplied by British Drug House) was used in this investigation.

Spectrophotometric method was adopted for the estimation of potassium indigo-sulphonate at any moment. The green region of the spectrum ($525 \mu\mu$) was chosen for this purpose, the *leuco*-dye having no extinction at this region. By plotting the ordinary spectrophotometric term $\log \tan \theta_2 - \log \tan \theta_1$ (θ_1 being obtained with water only) against concentration of the dye, a straight line was obtained. From this curve (Fig. 1), the concentration of potassium indigo-tetrasulphonate at any moment was calculated from the spectrophotometer reading at that moment.

FIG. 1.

TABLE I.

K-indigo-tetra-sulphonate.	Spectrophoto-meter readings.		$\text{Log} \frac{\tan \theta_2}{\tan \theta_1}$
	(with soln. in the cell θ_2).	(with water in the cell θ_1).	
$80 \cdot 0 \times 10^{-5} M$	$70^{\circ} 0$	$45^{\circ} 5$	$0 \cdot 4314$
$66 \cdot 0 \times 10^{-5}$	$67^{\circ} 2$	..	$0 \cdot 3689$
$50 \cdot 0 \times 10^{-5}$	$63^{\circ} 0$	..	$0 \cdot 2853$
$40 \cdot 0 \times 10^{-5}$	$59^{\circ} 5$	..	$0 \cdot 2224$
$25 \cdot 0 \times 10^{-5}$	$55^{\circ} 0$	..	$0 \cdot 1473$
$20 \cdot 0 \times 10^{-5}$	$54 \cdot 5$	..	$0 \cdot 1392$

The cell containing the reaction mixture was made absolutely air-tight as *leuco*-indigo is easily oxidised by air. It was observed that potassium indigo-tetrasulphonate does not get reduced when exposed to the light of wave-length $366 \mu\mu$ in presence of either tungstic acid sol or glucose separately. No dark reaction was observed when a mixture of glucose, potassium indigo-tetrasulphonate, sodium tungstate and hydrochloric acid was kept in the dark for more than 12 hours.

The extinction coefficient for $366 \mu\mu$ of *leuco*-indigo-sulphonate is very much greater than that of potassium indigo-sulphonate as determined by Moll thermopile and galvanometer. This will be evident from Table II.

TABLE II.

Substance taken.	Mol. ext. coeff. at $366 \mu\mu$.		
Pot.-indigo-tetrasulphonate	...	...	6,485 (ϵ_2)
<i>leuco</i> -Indigo-tetrasulphonate	...	...	27,594 (ϵ_1)
Tungstic acid sol	...	...	556 (ϵ_3)

The equation used in this paper is derived thus :—

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = K \cdot I (\text{fraction of light absorbed by tungstic acid sol}) \times C_1^2$$

$$= K I \frac{\epsilon_1 [T]}{\epsilon_1 [T] + \epsilon_2 (a - x) - \epsilon_3 x} \times C_1^2$$

$$= K I \cdot \frac{\epsilon_1 [T]}{\{\epsilon_1 [T] + \epsilon_2 a\} - (\epsilon_3 - \epsilon_2) x} \times C_s^n$$

$$= K I \cdot \frac{A}{A' + Bx} \cdot C_s^n$$

where $A = \epsilon_1 T$
 $B = \epsilon_3 - \epsilon_2$
 $A' = A + \epsilon_2 a$ (a , being the initial concentration of pot.indigo-tetrasulphonate).

and C_s^n is the surface conc. of reductant on the photoactive micelle.

The above equation on integration gives

$$K I C_s^n = \frac{A' x + \frac{Bx^2}{2}}{A t} \text{ where } t \text{ is reckoned in secs.}$$

For the same concentration of reductant present in excess,

$$K' I' = \frac{A' x + \frac{Bx^2}{2}}{A t} \dots (i)$$

TABLE III.

Experimental Results.

Tungstate = 0.03M. Glucose = 0.125M.
 HCl = 0.0478N. Indigo-tetrasulphonate
 = $37.6 \times 10^{-3} M$. ϕ_{28} of the system = 3.6.
 Temp. = 33°. I_{abs} (Intensity of absorbed
 radiation in ergs/cm²/sec.) = 8230.

Time.	Pot. indigo-sulphonate.	$K \times 10^7$ [from (i)].	$K \times 10^7$ (mean)	Conc. of glucose.	Conc. of indigo $\times 10^5$.	I_{abs} .	$K \times 10^7$ (i)
1. 0 sec.	$37.6 M \times 10^{-5}$			(a) 0.125M	76.9M	8230 ergs	1.43
2. 600	30.8	1.43 (from 1 & 2)		"	59.0	"	1.43
3. 1560	20.9	1.35 (from 1 & 3)	1.40	"	37.6	"	1.40
4. 2400	11.4	1.40 (from 1 & 4)		(b) 0.5M	82.3	7130	2.50
				"	37.4	"	2.43

TABLE IV.

Effect of varying the concentration of Pot. indigo-tetrasulphonate.

Temp. = 33°, ϕ_{28} = 3.61. Region
 - 366μμ. Tungstate = 0.03M.
 HCl = 0.0478M.

The above table shows that the equation (i) can be successfully applied to this particular reaction.

From Table IV it is evident that velocity constant is independent of the concentration of indigo-tetrasulphonate.

TABLE V.

Effect of varying the concentration of glucose.

Temp. = 33°. $p_n = 3.6$. Region — 366 μ . $d = 0.5$ cm. Tungstate = 0.03M, HCl = 0.0478N.

Conc. of Glucose.	Conc. of indigo $\times 10^5$.	I_{abs} .	$K \times 10^3$ (l)
(a) 0.5M	37.4×10^5 M	6650 ergs	2.19
0.25	"	"	1.58
0.125	"	"	1.10
0.0625	"	"	0.70
(b) 0.5M	72.0×10^5 M	3973	1.46
0.25	"	"	0.98
0.125	"	"	0.702

$1/K$ plotted against $1/C$ gives a straight line. (Fig. 2).

TABLE VI.

Effect of varying the concentration of HCl.

Temp. = 33°. $I_{abs} = 7130$. Tungstate = 0.03M. Glucose = 0.125M. Dye = 82.3×10^{-5} M.

Conc. of HCl.	p_n .	$K \times 10^3$ (l)
0.0478M	3.61	1.18
0.061	2.0	5.52
0.093	1.57	3.97

The velocity passes through a maximum at $p_n = 2$.

Temperature Coefficient of the Reaction.—The temperature coefficient is of the order of unity.

TABLE VII.

Effect of Varying the Intensity of Radiation absorbed.

Temp. = 33°. $p_n = 3.61$. Region — 366 μ . Tungstate = 0.03M. HCl = 0.0478M.

I_{abs} .	(a)		(b)		(c)	
	3973	2520	8230	3973	8230	6650
Conc. of glucose (M)	0.5	0.5	0.125	0.125	0.125	0.125
Conc. of indigo $\times 10^5$ (M)	76.9	76.9	76.9	76.9	37.0	37.0
$K \times 10^3$ (l).	1.46	0.93	1.43	0.702	1.40	1.10

The velocity constant, as is evident from the above table, is proportional to the intensity of radiation absorbed.

FIG. 2.

Quantum Efficiency of the Process.

Quantum efficiency is much less than unity.

A typical case (Table IVb) taken from the composition of the reaction mixture is given below:—

Conc. of tungstate = 0.03M. Conc. of HCl = 0.0478M.

Conc. of glucose = 0.5 M. Conc. of dye = $82.3 \times 10^{-5} M$.

$p_n = 3.61$. Mean wave-length = $366 \mu\mu$. Energy absorbed = 7134 ergs. per cm^2 /sec.

The reaction cell is 0.5 cm. thick and 2.7 sq. cm. in area.

Fraction of light quanta absorbed by tungstic acid sol per sec. per unit area

$$= \frac{7134 \times 366 \times 10^{-7} \times 2.7}{6.5 \times 10^{-87} \times 3 \times 10^{16}} \left[\frac{\epsilon_1 [T]}{\epsilon_1 [T] + \epsilon_2 [\text{Indigo}] + \epsilon_3 [\text{leucodye}]} \right]$$

$$= 36.09 \times 10^{14} \times 0.58 = 20.9 \times 10^{14}.$$

The initial conc. of indigo = $82.3 \times 10^{-5} M$.

After 31 mins. the conc. became = $50.5 \times 10^{-5} M$.

At that time $a-x = 50.5 \times 10^{-5} M$ (conc. of indigo-sulphonate)

$$x = 31.8 \times 10^{-5} M \text{ (conc. of leuco-dye)}$$

The no. of mols. transformed per sec.

$$= \frac{0.5 \times 2.7 \times 31.8 \times 10^{-5} \times 6.1 \times 10^{23}}{1000 \times 31 \times 60}$$

$$= 1.40 \times 10^{14}$$

$$\therefore \gamma (\text{Quantum efficiency}) = \frac{\text{No. of mols. transformed}}{\text{No. of quantum absorbed}}$$

$$= \frac{1.4 \times 10^{14}}{20.9 \times 10^{14}} = 0.067.$$

Dependence of the Velocity of Reaction on the State of Polarisation of Light.

TABLE VIII.

Region = 366 $\mu\mu$. Tungstate = 0.03M.
HCl = 0.0478N. Glucose = 0.5M.
K-indigo sulphonate = $76.8 \times 10^{-5} N$.
 $p_H = 3.61$.

Nature of light.	$I_{abs.}$	$K \times 10^3$ (θ)
Unpolarised	3973	1.46
l-Circularly polarised	1030	0.302
d-Circularly polarised	1030	0.197

TABLE IX.

Region = 366 $\mu\mu$. Tungstate = 0.02M.
HCl = 0.0318N. Temp. = 33°.
Glucose = 0.25M. K-indigo-sulphate
= $34.6 \times 10^{-5} N$. $p_H = 3.83$.

Nature of light.	$I_{abs.}$	$K \times 10^3$ (θ)
Unpolarised	5070	2.88
l-Circularly polarised	990	0.543
d-Circularly polarised	990	0.415

From Tables VIII and IX we find that $V_L > V_D$, the terms having their usual significance.

D I S C U S S I O N .

Any mechanism of reaction that may be proposed for this photochemical oxidation should be in a position to explain the following facts:

(a) The velocity constant is given by the equation

$$K'I = \frac{A'x + Bx^2/2}{A \cdot t} \quad \text{Eqn. ... (i)}$$

(b) The velocity constant increases as the concentration of glucose increases. If x/K is plotted against x/C_{glucose} , a straight line is obtained.

(c) The velocity passes through a maximum at $\phi_x \approx 2$.

(d) The temperature coefficient of the reaction is unity.

(e) The velocity constant is proportional to the intensity of radiation absorbed.

(f) Quantum efficiency is very low.

The sol surface is completely covered with a unimolecular layer of the dye molecules even at very low concentration of the dye. It is remarkable that the absorption of radiation by the dye molecules directly does not lead to their photoreduction by reaction with glucose. But a dye molecule can be brought into an activated state by receiving energy from the elementary spaces of tungstic acid sol surface which is also excited by the absorption of a quantum of radiation.

The initial velocity of reaction is given by

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = K_1 C_s^n I$$

where I is the radiant energy absorbed per sec. by the elementary spaces of the tungstic acid sol surface and C_s^n , the surface concentration of reductant.

But with the progress of reaction, the *leuco*-dye is formed and the photo-sensitive sol surface begins to be covered with the molecules of *leuco*-dye.

The fraction of the surface so covered by the *leuco*-dye becomes useless for purpose of photoreduction and hence

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = K_1 C_s^n I_0 \frac{\epsilon_1 [T]}{\epsilon_1 [T] + \epsilon_2 (a-x) + \epsilon_3 x}$$

which on integration gives the equation (i).

This equation (i) has been found to hold good.

The rate of oxidation of glucose also depends on the surface concentration of glucose.

But since, according to Langmuir's hypothesis, C_s^a is given by

$$\frac{K_3 C_s^a}{K_4 + K_3 C_s^a} \text{ where } C_s^a \text{ is the bulk concentration of glucose in solution.}$$

$1/K'$ plotted against $1/C_{\text{glucose (bulk)}}$ should give a straight line which has been found to be true.

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